

Electrified cascade PCM concept for Thermal Energy Storage in a CSP plant

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Abstract

Non-dispatchable renewable technologies cannot completely decarbonize the electricity generation sector, while dispatchable technologies such as Concentrated Solar Power are too expensive for a wide commercial deployment. Aiming to reduce the cost of this technology, this document presents an electrified PCM thermal energy storage in cascade configuration with hybridization capabilities. This configuration can store energy at temperatures up to 610 °C using state-of-the-art CSP technology, which enables the use of advanced power cycles such as supercritical CO₂ cycles. A cascade configuration of the PCM is described to reduce the hysteresis effect generated due to the charge/discharge of the latent TES using a sensible current, and a final electrified step is proposed to ensure a maximum temperature output of the TES.

Keywords: Phase Change Material ; Thermal Energy Storage ; Concentrated Solar Power

Introduction

Renewable energy technologies have become a major topic due to global warming with expected cumulative investments between 13 and 38 USD trillion between 2016 and 2050 [1]. The growth among these renewable technologies has been led by solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind, with a final share of more than 57% of the total renewable installed capacity worldwide [2].

However, these technologies are non-dispatchable and as such their growth is limited in order to ensure proper management of the electricity grid [3]. Concentrated Solar Power (CSP), on the other hand, can be fully dispatchable once a Thermal Energy Storage (TES) system is installed. The cost of this technology is still too high to compete with other renewable technologies if the dispatchability of the generated energy is not taken into consideration [4], but the potential for cost reductions is also high.

Advanced thermal cycles such as supercritical CO₂ cycles can further increase the efficiency of this technology and reduce its costs, but to do so, temperatures up to 600 °C are required. The state-of-the-art TES technology, solar salt storage in direct configuration in two tanks for CSP plants in tower configuration, can store energy up to 565-580 °C, not enough for the supercritical CO₂ power cycles to be cost-effective.

In this work, an innovative thermal energy storage based on Phase Change Material (PCM) is presented,

able to reach operating temperatures up to 610 °C and enabling the use of supercritical CO₂ power cycles. This TES addresses the low thermal conductivity of PCM by using metal wools [5], and include internal electric heaters to work as a power-to-heat reservoir, further increasing the capacity factor of the plant while improving grid stability services at the same time. These electric heaters grant the CSP plant the ability to hybridise with other collocated renewable technologies, typically photovoltaic, or even from the grid with PPAs.

Plant concept

The proposed power plant has the same configuration as the typical CSP plant: i) a solar field, ii) a thermal storage system, iii) a heat exchanger and iv) a power cycle. In the solar field (i), the energy from the sun is concentrated using mirrors called heliostats into a receiver, where the energy is transferred to a heat transfer fluid (HTF). The HTF transfers the heat to the storage system (ii) or to the power block (iv) through the heat exchanger (iii). Thanks to the use of electric heaters embedded in the TES, this plant can easily hybridize with a collocated photovoltaic plant or take advantage of excess renewable energy from the grid (Figure 1).

Figure 1 CSP plant configuration

The HTF selected for the proposed plant is the same as most CSP plants in tower configuration use worldwide, solar salt (40/60 wt% $\text{KNO}_3/\text{NaNO}_3$). This binary salt has excellent properties and is economically viable, but its maximum operating temperature is limited to a degradation phenomenon that occurs when the salts are kept at high temperatures for a prolonged period of time. This degradation mechanism is time-related, as described by Bell et Al. [6] and McConohy et Al. [7] and thus, the authors propose to only use the solar salts as HTF and store the energy in an indirect system based on PCM. This configuration allows to increase the maximum operative temperature of the salts up to 610°C for small periods of time without degradation.

TES

The proposed TES configuration is based on latent heat storage using phase change materials. The advantage of the high energy density of latent heat storage and the typical affordable cost of the materials is challenged by their low thermal conductivity, which poses a threat to the commercial viability of the solution. Several researchers have been actively working on this topic and have proposed different solutions such as the use of nano-additives, fins, or graphite foams [8], [9], [10]. All these options have their advantages, but they have an important impact on the final cost of the solution. Metal wools, on the other hand, are cheap, do not impose a large volume increase and can strongly increase the thermal conductivity [5]. This thermal conductivity enhancement is anisotropic, allowing the horizontal direction in vertical tanks to be favoured and thus promoting a thermocline behaviour.

One of the advantages of using latent heat energy is its capability of providing energy at constant temperature. This is very useful for certain purposes but becomes a liability when the HTF works only in the sensible phase. When a PCM is charged with a sensible current, the temperature of the HTF has to always be higher than the temperature of the PCM and the opposite when

discharging. As it can be seen in Figure 2, this creates a thermal hysteresis between the charge and discharge stages, reducing the maximum output temperature of the tank, reducing the tank efficiency, and hindering cyclic operations. The solar salt used as HTF has very strict temperature limits of operation: 280°C as lower limit due to freezing issues and 610°C as upper limit due to degradation phenomena. The thermal hysteresis between charge and discharge becomes, in this way, a major drawback for the use of PCM storage in the CSP industry. In addition to this issue, the high temperature difference of up to 300°C at the start of the charge or discharge phases between the PCM and the HTF poses a mechanical problem with a difficult engineering solution. This can be partially mitigated by using only the latent regime of the PCM, at the cost of reducing the energy density and increasing the mass of PCM for the same energy output.

Figure 2 Heat distribution in a PCM during charge and discharge

Cascade configuration

To address both issues, the authors propose to use a cascade configuration made of several PCM that melts at different temperatures between the lower and upper HTF limits, as displayed in Figure 3. In this configuration, the thermal hysteresis is greatly reduced, as is the temperature difference among each step of the cascade, built in independent tanks called modules.

To reduce the hysteresis, each step should have a similar melting energy, which implies that each module will have a different amount of PCM to cover for the different melting enthalpies of the selected materials. Also, the temperature ranges should be evenly distributed. This also helps to reduce the mechanical stress due to temperature differences.

Figure 3 Heat distribution of a cascade PCM during charge and discharge

Figure 4 Heat distribution of an electrified cascade PCM during charge and discharge

When considering the availability of PCM in the required range, during the preliminary investigations of the HYBRIDplus project from which this investigation has been carried out, 67 PCM candidates have been identified. Studies performed up to date have discarded some of these materials due to hygroscopy, corrosiveness with metal wools, poor performance, or cost [11], but there are still several candidates under study.

Electrified cascade configuration

Each module is internally electrified, and as such the energy can be provided partially or totally by excess electricity from the collocated PV plant or from the grid. This hybridization does not affect the normal operation of the plant, but just increases its operative hours and thus its capacity factor. To further reduce the thermal hysteresis and guarantee the maximum temperature output from the TES, another PCM step is included in the cascade with a melting temperature above the maximum operating temperature of the salts (Figure 4).

This PCM is not expected to be charged thermally, but only electrically, with thermal discharge. Using this configuration, the plant can operate at its maximum temperature defined by the degradation of the solar salt, maximizing the efficiency of the power cycle and ensuring constant temperature on the TES discharge.

Concept demonstration

The cascade concept proposed in this document is going to be demonstrated in a pilot plant under construction in the premises of the University of Seville. This pilot plant will test three PCM modules with different melting temperatures in cascade configuration using solar salts as HTF and with embedded electric heaters to move the technology up to a TRL5-6. For this pilot plant, the PCM modules will have a shell and tube configuration with the PCM on the shell and the HTF flowing through the tubes. All modules will use metal wools as heat enhancement method, favouring the horizontal plane in order to generate a thermocline inside the tank.

The electric heater capabilities will be emulated with three different configurations, one for each module: immersed heater, ohmic heating and magnetic charge [12]. To simulate the solar field, an inline electric heater for the solar salts used as HTF for the thermal charge will be installed, and the discharge energy will be dissipated to the atmosphere.

With the aim of learning from the experience, the installation of the PCM modules will be sequential. The low temperature module will be installed first, with an immersion heater for electrification. With the lessons learnt during the first tests, a second module will be installed, and then a third. For the second and third modules, different electrification methods will be studied. At the end of the experimentation campaign, it is expected to have the three modules working in cascade.

Conclusions

This document presents the electrified cascade concept used for the PCM-TES of the HYBRIDplus project. The cascade configuration reduces thermal hysteresis effect of charging/discharging a latent heat storage with a sensible current, reducing the temperature difference between charge and discharge. At the same time, the thermal stress is greatly reduced thanks to this configuration.

A proposal of improvement with the addition of a final electric stage for maximum output temperature is presented, ensuring temperatures up to 610 °C in the discharge and enabling the coupling with advanced supercritical CO₂ power cycles.

In order to obtain the optimum number of steps for the cascade configuration, a techno-economic analysis should be performed, since increasing the number of steps reduces the thermal hysteresis and increases performance but increases the complexity and the final cost. There is a minimum number of steps based on the maximum thermal gradient of the module for mechanical considerations.

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